

Wind Energy and Grid Integration in Sri Lanka

Lessons Learned from the April 2018 AHK trip

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It is likely that the situation in Sri Lanka may change with time and that this document is not a full representation of those conditions. The reader is encouraged to conduct their own investigations before taking any decisions based on this document.

This report is partly based on experience gathered during a trip to Sri Lanka in April 2018 that was paid for by the German Chambers of Commerce (Deutsche Auslandshandelskammern, AHK). This report does not represent the opinion of the AHK.

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Executive Summary

Currently renewable energy – including wind, solar, biomass, and hydroelectric plants – supplies around 35% of Sri Lanka’s needs. In 2017, 124 MW of installed wind energy and 42 MW of solar energy capacity contributed around 5% of the total energy generation.

The Sri Lanka Government has pledged to generate 100% of Sri Lanka’s electricity from renewable sources by 2050. Sri Lanka has the opportunity to plan now for the renewable-energy based electrical system of the future and avoid challenges experienced elsewhere. This transition will require new technical approaches, but could leverage international experience and established energy transition pathways. A 2017 report prepared by the Asian Development Bank (ADB) suggests that this transition is feasible without raising the cost burden on consumers.

Local public- and private sector experience and know-how will need to be coupled with international expertise to provide solutions that are sympathetic to local needs. Specific actions include a “hard talk” between stakeholders; the provision of basic resource data; identifying development zones; exploring unbundling the CEB; a new grid integration study; exploring the impacts of electrical vehicles; revisiting a grid interconnection to India; developing workforces; developing entrepreneurial opportunities; and demonstration projects for energy storage, microgrids, offshore wind, and biofuel-powered thermal power plants.

Some of these development activities can be supported by regional and international groups such as the ADB, business groups such as the AHK, and through international development support through specialist organizations

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1 About this document

This document describes on a strategic level how wind energy could contribute to Sri Lanka's renewable energy goals, and the potential implications for the Sri Lanka electrical grid. This document is based on information gathered by the author during a trip to Sri Lanka with the German Chambers of Commerce (Deutsche Auslandshandelskammern, AHK) in April 2018 and later research.

This document is intended for readers in development and business agencies who are interested in the grid integration of renewable energy sources. Readers should note that due to the multidisciplinary and international nature of this work that there are sections that are simplified and that expert assistance would be appropriate. Detailed references are not provided.

As background, the purpose of electrical grids is explained in Section 2. The current state of the Sri Lankan electrical grid is described in Section 3. Section 4 describes the Government of Sri Lanka's recent commitment to 100% renewable energy by 2050. The Ceylon Electricity Board (CEB)'s 2017 Long Term Generation Expansion Plan (LTGEP) is summarized in Section 5. Typical pathways for deploying renewable energy are illustrated in Section 6. Conclusions are given in Section 7.

The reader may wish to read this document together with the 2017 LTGEP [2] and the Public Utilities Commission of Sri Lanka (PUCSL, the electricity sector regulator) July 2017 decision on the LTGEP.

2 The Role of an Electrical Grid

The basic purpose of an electrical grid is to connect generators to consumers. The role of the grid operator is to match the supply and demand of electricity at all times and ensure that the frequency of electricity stays in a narrow band.

An important characteristic of today's electrical networks is that the demand for electricity is driven by users, who expect electricity at the flick of a switch. Also, in today's networks there is no practical way to store energy. Therefore, the grid operator matches supply with demand by adjusting the amount of generation. This is usually done by forecasting demand and scheduling the required generation in advance. This process is known as dispatch and typically runs up to a day ahead in blocks of a few minutes to an hour, depending on the system. Thermal systems (coal, gas) and hydroelectrical plants are often described as "dis-

patchable" because a thermal power plant can be relied upon to deliver power on demand unless there is unplanned maintenance. And, thermal plants (particularly gas-fired) can sometimes be operated with variable output power to help in load following.

Power plants can respond to small and fast changes in demand through a process called frequency response. Because thermal-powered generators are typically large spinning masses, they store energy as inertia. If the load on the grid increases, energy is extracted from the spinning mass of the generator. This causes the rotational speed of the generator to start to drop, and reduces the frequency of electricity across the whole grid. This *inertial response* is an inherent function of most types of grid-connected rotating generator. This can also temporarily store excess energy (oversupply) in the spinning mass of the generator, increasing the frequency of the grid. These deviations from the target frequency can be controlled by increasing or reducing the fuel supply to the generator unit, which is called *governor response* or *primary response* and happens over time periods of 1 – 100 seconds. Sustained demand increase needs to be offset by increasing supply. To do this, the grid operator can automatically add already-committed generation. This is known as automated grid control (AGC) or *secondary response* and is constrained by the amount of available spare generating capacity on the system.

Ramping, starting, and stopping thermal generators adds to the cost of energy from thermal power plants, because of the extra loads and maintenance requirements that are incurred. This cost has led to a preference to operate thermal power plants as so-called 'base load' plants where they are always operating at their most efficient power setting and as such they may not be able to provide secondary response. Some facilities, typically gas, are designed to operate with very varying outputs (i.e. can contribute to secondary response) and so are sometimes described as load-following plants.

By comparison, many renewable energy electricity generators including wind, solar, and hydroelectric power plants are fuelled by the weather and are therefore inherently variable. Without energy storage, their predictability is governed by the accuracy of the weather forecast that the grid operator uses, which makes dispatch harder and may result in the need for reserve energy sources or for investment in load-following thermal plants. Furthermore, early wind and solar energy systems lacked the ability to provide inertial response or load following, leading to a change in grid dynamics. These

are well-known challenges for grid operators when integrating variable renewable energy [1].

In practice, grid integration of variable renewable energy sources can be enabled on the supply side by:

1. Reducing the variability of supply to the grid through local storage
2. Use of grid-connected energy storage for balancing and regulation
3. Increasing the predictability of the power generation through forecasting and observations
4. Use of markets for balancing and regulation
5. Interconnection with other networks.

Depending on the system design, storage could play many different roles in the grid [see e.g. 10]. Storage could be large-scale (tens of megawatt hours of stored energy and tens of megawatts power) and directly connected to the grid as a separate facility which would let it fill production shortfalls. Storage could also be integrated in to the weather-driven renewable energy system directly to provide grid services. However, storage has a capital cost, and its use also requires a change in grid operator strategies.

Demand-side measures can also enable integration of variable renewable energy. Measures include:

1. Load forecasting
2. Load management including load shedding and load shifting
3. Provision of grid services, e.g., from wind turbine or solar panel power electronics [8].

Combining supply-side and demand-side measures can allow an electrical grid to function with a large amount of variable renewable energy. For example, the Irish grid operator announced in 2018 that it was able to operate with up to 65% of variable renewable energy at any time.¹ The amount of generation on the Irish grid is similar to Sri Lanka at 3,000 to 4,000 MW. Although Ireland is an island, the Irish grid is connected to the mainland United Kingdom through two 500-MW interconnections.

Increasing the use of renewable energy could conceivably lead to a situation where the grid is a network of distributed renewable energy generators such as rooftop and utility-scale solar, multi-megawatt wind plants, small and large hydro, and biomass plants, all capable of supporting the grid [7]. These could be balanced by a regional or

¹See [EirGrid news release from 13 April 2018](#)

national electrical network of reserve generators and grid-connected storage. In such a network frequency control would be a result of control decisions rather than an inherent response of a rotating generator, while dispatch would likely be market-driven. The grid operator's role would then likely be to facilitate trading and provide infrastructure. Together these measures are often referred to as the 'Smart Grid' and can be seen developing in parts of the USA and Europe.

3 Sri Lanka's Electrical Power System

Sri Lanka has a nationwide synchronous electric power system that provides power to more than 98% of the population [See e.g. Fig. 1.5 of 2].

The power system is operated by the Ceylon Electricity Board (CEB). CEB is a vertically-integrated utility that develops, owns, and operates most of the generators, balances the supply and demand on the system, plans dispatch, builds and maintains transmission, provides distribution to customers, and carries out strategic planning. CEB also buys power from independent power producers (IPPs), including thermal plants for balancing, mini hydro, solar and wind plants. The total generation capacity is around 4 GW (Table 1). All fossil fuels used for electrical generation are imported.

Sri Lanka's power system is an islanded system with no large-scale storage from pumped storage or batteries. Balancing of supply and demand is carried out primarily by dispatch of generators and load management. Individual generators are limited in size to reduce the effect of unplanned outage but are also capable of running at part load and rapid ramping to allow load following. An interconnection to India has been explored several times but there are no initiatives at this time [See e.g. Section 4.5 of 2]. Building the interconnection would be a major undertaking.

The Government of Sri Lanka has committed to international climate change temperate goals including ratifying COP21, and has a desire to maintain or improve air quality and protect the environment in Sri Lanka. Partly as a result of these commitments, there has been some development of wind and solar energy on the island. This appears to follow plans developed in conjunction with NREL in the early 2000s [12].

The first wind power plant was built and commissioned in Sri Lanka in 2010. Since then 127 MW of wind power in 15 projects has been connected to the grid. This development was led and managed by local companies with a combination of local and

international financing. Turbines were sourced internationally and installed by local companies.

CEB announced a tender for the construction of a 100 MW wind power plant at Mannar in 2017. This would be financed partly by the CEB, and partly by an Asian Development Bank loan. CEB did not award a contract, and the tender reopened in 2018. The Mannar wind power plant should now be operational by 2020.

Net metering was implemented in 2010 to encourage local solar power. Installations were limited to annual net zero consumption. There are now some 5,500 systems totalling 40 MW [p. 5-14 of 2].

4 100% Renewable Energy by 2050

Sri Lanka pledged to use only renewable energy for electricity generation by 2050 at the UNFCCC Conference of Parties in Marakech in 2016.²

A joint report by the Asian Development Bank (ADB) and United Nations Development Program (UNDP) published in 2017 described several scenarios by which Sri Lanka could transition to 100% renewable energy by 2050 without raising the burden on consumers [11]. Such a transition was expected to lead to large savings and position Sri Lanka as a regional technological leader.

The key challenges faced by Sri Lanka in this transition [identified in 11, and elsewhere] include:

- A large amount of investment required in generation, transmission, and distribution
- Inadequacy of ancillary systems to support the grid in high renewable energy scenarios
- Lack of proper incentives to develop renewable energy capacity
- High current cost of renewable energy
- Lack of local R&D
- Slow development of rooftop solar
- Vulnerability of large hydro to climate variability and change.

The ADB / UNDP study notes that a transition would also require innovation such as smart meters, the use of the Internet of Things, improved communications, and automated distributed systems [see p. 28 of 11].

Sri Lanka now faces a fundamental question about how to promote and integrate more weather-

²See the outcome document of the CVF High Level Meeting at UNFCCC COP22 on Friday 18 November 2016.

driven renewable energy. This transition could follow the pathways of the past by trying to adapt existing infrastructure and follow the example of Europe and the USA. Alternatively Sri Lanka could consciously look to the future and implement policies and infrastructure decisions that would support a decentralized, renewable energy-based future.

5 The CEB's 2017 Long Term Generation Expansion Plan

According to the LTGEP, "The Ceylon Electricity Board (CEB) is under a statutory duty to develop and maintain an efficient, coordinated and economical system of Electricity Supply for the whole of Sri Lanka. Therefore, CEB is required to generate or acquire sufficient amount of electricity to satisfy the demand." As part of this statutory duty, CEB publishes long-term generation expansion plans every two years. The most recent LTGEP was published in April 2017 and covers the period from 2018 to 2037 [2].

The LTGEP was approved with some minor modifications by the PUCSL in July 2017.³ That gave CEB the go-ahead to commence procurement for new generating plants for the years 2018 - 2028.

A summary of the approved plan follows. Comments are explicitly identified.

5.1 Demand growth

The LTGEP Base Case assumes that demand for electricity in Sri Lanka will grow at around 6.8% in 2018–2020, and then at 5% per year through 2037. This will lead to peak demand doubling in the next 20 years. The increase in demand is predicted using multivariate linear regression, following relationships derived from data for prior years. The demand growth is driven mostly by economic and population growth [p. 3-6 of 2]. The LTGEP anticipates linear growth in per-capita consumption. The consumption per unit of economic output is expected to grow slightly [see Section 3.3.2 of 2]. Peak electricity demand currently occurs in the evening. The peak is expected to shift towards daytime by 2037. The forecast peak demand can be covered entirely by non-renewable resources.

In the PUCSL decision, the CEB was directed to "revisit and refine ... Demand forecast (specially the off peak demand and load factor)".

Comment: *Daily and seasonal demand profiles, and the amount of energy required in Sri Lanka, could*

³See [PUCSL news release from July 2017](#)

change with widespread adoption of electric vehicles or other electrification measures.

5.2 Base case and other solutions

Several case studies were considered for the LTGEP. These included a base case, increased or reduced demand compared to the base case, changes in the discount rate, and increased fuel prices. Fuel diversification cases were also used to explore the effect of policy changes on the cost of energy and security of supply, and included the use of nuclear power [Table E.3 in 2]. CEB considers the base case plan described here to be the lowest cost solution to the most probable scenario.

Table 1 summarizes the installed capacity and energy generated from each energy source.

Comment: *The cost difference between some of the scenarios in the LTGEP is less than 10% and depends mainly on the discount rate, then the demand forecast, and then on the fuel mix [see Table E.3 2]. The PUCSL recognized that a small change in external costs would make a gas-dominated mix cheaper than a coal dominated mix. It is therefore possible that the approved plan will result in more expensive energy and higher carbon emissions than might have been achieved with one of the other plans.*

5.3 Actions in the next five years (2018-2022)

The LTGEP forecasts a risk of capacity shortage in 2018-2023. CEB recommends covering these with 320 MW of new reciprocating engine power plants (i.e. fossil-fueled, thermal power plants) by 2018 and 105 MW of natural gas-powered plants by 2020 as peakers and for black starts [see p. E-10 of 2].

187 MW of hydro plants are also planned to be commissioned between 2019 and 2022. These will also be used as low-cost peaking plants.

The LTGEP also included procurement of 270 MW of wind energy capacity by 2020, and a further 75 MW by 2022.

5.4 Meeting longer-term needs

The Base Case plan proposes installing coal and gas-powered generators to meet projected demand, with some wind, solar, and biomass (Table 1). Under the 2018 – 2028 investment plan authorised by the PUCSL, a total of 655 MW of wind and 950 MW of solar capacity will be installed by 2028. In contrast, 150-600 MW of thermal powered plant will be installed each year in the same period.

The total investment in new plants (not currently

committed) in the 20-year base case plan is calculated as approximately USD 14.568 Billion [Section 7.2 of 2]. This includes several projects per year with total annual expenditure exceeding USD 200 Million for Major Hydro and thermal plants, and over USD 100 for wind and solar plants [Figure 8.2 and Tables 8.2 and 8.3 of 2].

Comment: *An accurate comparison of the different energy scenarios requires comparing the costs of infrastructure such as a coal jetty and gas handling facility. As far as can be seen, this has been included in the fossil fuel plants in the LTGEP. The deployment of wind, solar, and other renewable energy might require some investment in port facilities, roads, and other logistics, but such infrastructure could be leveraged by other industries and their costs to renewable energy would thereby be reduced.*

5.5 Losses

Net losses – including transmission and distribution – are expected to drop from 9.88% to 9% over the course of the plan (Table E.1). These are target losses and the LTGEP notes that they should be adjusted for the actual energy sources used.

5.6 Assumptions about renewable energy

Predicting the amount and timing of energy that is available from renewable energy systems requires accurate information about the location, magnitude, and timing of the resource [i.e. wind speed, solar radiation; see 4], the potential available land, the performance of the systems that would be installed, their reliability, and the ability to get the energy to consumers [see 3].

Results from a limited renewable energy integration study are included in the LTGEP. That study assumes a limited build of wind energy in defined locations, rather than a market-driven approach.

The study assumes wind plant capacity factors of 19 to 36% and solar capacity factors of around 16% (Table 5.8 of the LTGEP). Also, the study assumed a wind system availability of 91% [p. 5-17 of 2] and a solar system availability of 90% [p. 5-18 of 2]. These capacity factors do not appear to be based on a realistic, optimized wind or solar plant design. For example, the study assumes 50-m wind turbine hub heights in the hill country and 80 m elsewhere, which is relatively short by current standards [p. 5-17 of 2].

Comment: *These performance assumptions directly penalize future renewable energy developments because they reduce the estimated amount of energy from wind turbines and solar panels compared to*

Table 1. Installed capacity and electricity generation in 2018 compared to 2037 under the LTGEP Base Case Plan

Source	2018		2037 Base Case Plan	
	Installed capacity ¹ (MW)	Generation ² (% annual total)	Installed capacity ¹ (MW)	Generation ² (% annual total)
Hydro	1,370	23.4	2,211	11.6
- existing major	1,370		1,370	9.0
- new major	-		241	1.2
- pumped hydro	-		600	1.4
Other renewables	727	13.0	3,431	20.6
- mini hydro ³	344		544	
- wind ³	144		1,349	
- solar ³	210		1,442	
- biomass ³	39	1.7	119	2.0
Thermal	2,172	64.3	5,141	67.7
- existing	-		1,171	12.4
- new coal	-		2,502	41.1
- new 35 MW gas	-		105	-
- new gas combined cycle	-		1,363	14.3
Total capacity (MW)	4,269		10,783	
Peak demand (MW)	2,738		6,372	
Total generation (GWh)		16,291		41,991

Data sources are given as superscripts in the table. The sources are 1: Annex 7.2 of the LTGEP; 2: Annex 7.3 of the LTGEP (given as % of total generation including biomass); 3: Table 5.7 of the LTGEP. No generation data were found for renewables. Small discrepancies may be observed between sources that do not impact the observations of this document.

what could be achieved. For example, availability over 95% is common as third-party support companies become established. Also, the USA and Europe have seen typical wind plant capacity factors increase from 25 to 30% in the early 2000s to well over 35% in the last few years. Finally, costs have fallen as a result of competition and as production matures. And, the levelized cost of electricity has come down as a result. Similar advantageous changes to the availability and performance of renewable energy and the cost of electricity in Sri Lanka might be realized by:

1. Increasing power output by using new solar panel materials or taller turbines with larger rotors
2. Reducing capital costs by optimizing designs, changing construction methods, and leveraging new infrastructure
3. Reducing operational costs, for example by using wind turbines designed to work at higher temperatures and salinity than elsewhere, and
4. Reducing financing costs by decreasing energy production forecast uncertainty.

In the PUCSL decision, the CEB was directed to “revisit and refine ... Investment plan with ORE absorption levels to achieve 60% of electricity generation from Renewable energy sources (including Large Hydro plants) by year 2030”.

Comment: The LTGEP frequently lumps wind, solar, and other renewable energy together as ‘other renewable energy (ORE)’, which hides their individual contribution to the energy balance. Future LTGEPs should identify wind, solar, and other types of renewable energy separately as each has unique characteristics.

5.7 Planning for renewable energy

As was noted in Section 2 of this document, there are several challenges with integrating variable renewable energy sources into an electrical grid. Section 8.6 of The LTGEP recommends several steps to help this process, including a day-ahead forecasting system, renewable energy desk, granting curtailment rights to the grid operator, electrical network strengthening, and variable generation base-load plants. It also proposes reviewing planning methods every two years.

Comment: These measures should help the CEB to predict the power produced by weather-driven renewable energy and plan dispatch and grid operations appropriately. A public tender for forecasting services would help ensure access to international expertise. The need for curtailment should be mitigated in the near term by effective forecasts and de-loadable base load plants, and in the longer term through storage.

5.8 Islanded system

The LTGEP assumes the Sri Lankan electrical grid will be an islanded network with no energy storage.

Comment: *Assuming an islanded grid with no energy storage skews the LTGEP scenarios towards a thermally-dominated future because of the need for generators that can be used for grid control and balancing.*

6 Perspectives on Deploying Renewable Energy in Sri Lanka

The main drivers to the deployment of renewable energy in Sri Lanka seem to be national commitments to international climate change agreements, coupled with local environmental or air-quality concerns, and the need for a reliable domestic energy supply.

Countries tend to follow broadly similar pathways to large-scale deployment of renewable energy [6]. These pathways generally involve identifying and mitigating barriers associated with four factors that are specific to each country:

- Political framework and market regulation
- Infrastructure capacity and technical feasibility
- Economic viability and financing
- Acceptance and awareness raising.

A list of questions to help identify barriers related to each factor is included in [6]. A detailed assessment of Sri Lanka's progress in identifying and mitigating barriers associated with each of these factors is out of the scope of this document. However, some barriers are apparent as a result of the author's visit to Sri Lanka in April 2018 and subsequent research. Those barriers are described in the following subsections together with possible mitigating actions.

The following possible mitigating actions are described with the awareness that they may already be happening in Sri Lanka, and are included here for completeness. Because of the fast-moving nature of renewable energy technology, existing studies may need to be reviewed against current best practice and updated.

6.1 Political framework and market regulation

Although a clear political framework and market regulation appears to exist in Sri Lanka, there remains uncertainty around energy demand and how it might relate to renewable energy generation.

For example, the temporal and spatial distribution of renewable energy resources is not well known. And, from the outside, it seems there may be a lack of exchange between stakeholders in Sri Lanka.

The following actions are suggested.

6.1.1 Build stakeholder groups

Stakeholder associations have been found to be very useful in Europe and north America in providing a coherent voice and enabling dialog between different groups and the Government.

Suggested action: *The Sri Lankan private sector may wish to strengthen groups such as the Wind Power Association of Sri Lanka (founded 2010, possibly dormant), or set up new stakeholder groups as required.*

6.1.2 Facilitate a "Hard Talk"

The UNECE and partners have developed the "Hard Talk" concept to bring stakeholders together to explore each of the four factors and document potential solutions [see Section 6 of 6]. Hard Talks are events that facilitate exchange between decision makers, renewable energy developers, investors and technology providers in the public and private sectors. The outcome is ways to improve the investment climate for renewable energy.

Suggested action: *The Sri Lankan Government and CEB could work with the GIZ to hold a "Hard Talk" about deploying renewable energy in Sri Lanka.*

6.1.3 Provide foundational resource data

The LTGEP renewable energy resource estimation [see Section 5.6 of 2] uses limited wind and solar data to determine the energy available for wind and solar resources. This may result in an underestimation of the potential resource and its geographic spread. This has implications for zoning and for the LTGEP.

Experience in the USA and elsewhere has shown that a high temporal and spatial renewable energy resource database is necessary to identify commercially relevant renewable energy resources, including wind at multiple heights, solar energy, and biomass. These resource databases may need to achieve 1-minute temporal resolution and spatial resolution on the order of 1 km or less over a period of up to 20 years. This resolution captures spatial and temporal gradients and the variability of the resource, and is required for grid integration studies. The long duration helps ensure that potential extreme cases are considered.

Suggested action: The CEB should commission a renewable energy resource data study to provide the foundational data required to support the widespread deployment and integration of renewable energy. Because of the specialist skills required and potential high costs, the CEB could partner with an international development organization such as the Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) or United States Agency for International Development (USAID) to co-fund and produce such a study.

6.1.4 Quantify the potential for offshore wind energy

Offshore wind energy offers many potential benefits over land-based wind. The wind resources are often better and more reliable offshore and turbines can be larger, leading to higher energy production. Also, there are larger areas available for development offshore than on land. However, offshore wind is expensive and technically challenging because of the environment. An overview of the drivers and history of offshore wind energy deployment in Germany can be found in [5].

In Europe, elsewhere in Asia, and in the USA, initial offshore wind energy developments have usually been in water where monopiles or jacketed foundations can be used. These technologies allow wind turbines to be deployed in water up to 60 m deep. An overview of the process of identifying the offshore wind potential for the USA can be found in a 2016 report by the US National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [9]. Similar capabilities exist at the German Fraunhofer Institute for Wind Energy Systems (Fraunhofer IWES) and at several international consultancies.⁴

Suggested action: The Government of Sri Lanka may wish to partner with NREL or Fraunhofer IWES to assess the potential for offshore wind energy in Sri Lanka. This could be combined with the preparation of a resource database and a grid integration study.

6.1.5 Identify renewable energy development zones

Development of renewable energy sources can be eased by identifying zones in which development of commercial-scale renewable energy plants will be encouraged. Development areas are usually defined based on potentially relevant resources (e.g. capacity factors that can be achieved), distance to loads, terrain limitations (e.g. low slope angles), proximity to national parks, ethnological and ecological resources, and other constraints. Identifying development zones allows both utilities

⁴See similar studies for Gujarat and Tamil Nadu supported by the European Union

and developers to prepare for large-scale deployment through activities such as wind resource measurement campaigns and high-resolution modeling, transmission studies and construction, and stakeholder engagement.

Suggested action: The Government of Sri Lanka should identify renewable energy development zones around the country which could be suitable for wind, solar, biomass, and other renewable energy technologies.

6.1.6 Explore unbundling the CEB

The CEB is a nationally-owned vertically integrated utility. This model is now unusual and has been replaced in many countries by a combination of privatized independent power producers, transmission system operators, and power distribution companies. This separation encourages organizational focus and efficiency without reducing grid reliability. There are many different ways of implementing markets to the electrical grid and all solutions need to be tailored to Sri Lankan needs. Privatization would also generate funds for the Government.

Suggested action: The CEB and Sri Lankan Government may wish to explore the potential to unbundle and privatize the CEB. The CEB may find it useful to explore the UK Government's experience with privatizing the UK's Central Electricity Generating Board (CEGB) in the 1990s, Germany's experiences with the Energiewende, and other privatization actions.

6.2 Infrastructure capacity and technical feasibility

Some demand side activities are being taken by other agencies in Sri Lanka [p. 3-15 of 2] but their effects are not included in the LTGEP. Supply side activities appear limited to the use of major hydro and gas to balance variable loads.

The major barriers to the integration of wind and other renewable energy in Sri Lanka appear to be the lack of a forecasting system, the lack of links between energy sectors (e.g., the use of waste for generating electricity), the lack of an interconnection with India, and complex planning procedures.

6.2.1 Carry out renewable energy grid integration studies

The scenarios studied in the LTGEP do not include high penetration of renewable energy with modern supply- and demand-side integration measures.

One foreseeable scenario is distributed renewable energy generation backed up by storage, major

hydroelectric and pumped storage facilities, and an interconnection to India. The scenario could be extended to include large-scale electrification of the Sri Lanka transport sector through the introduction of electrical vehicles, or the use of power-to-gas to reduce the dependency on fuel imports.

While such transitions may seem impractical or unrealistic at this time, such a forward-looking grid integration study could show potential avenues for development. The successful implementation of such technologies would transform Sri Lanka into a regional leader in reliable clean energy, offering the potential to export such know-how internationally.

Suggested action: A renewable energy grid integration study could be carried out by CEB together with a private contractor, or with third parties such as USAID and NREL in the USA, or Fraunhofer, GIZ, and ZSW in Germany. More details are provided in Section 7.

6.2.2 Model impacts of electric vehicles

The widespread adoption of electrically-powered vehicles in Sri Lanka would potentially result in an increase in the consumption of electricity but also make a large amount of battery capacity available for use in balancing the grid. Furthermore, the introduction of electric vehicles could be coupled with the construction of distributed or rooftop solar panels and battery systems, which might reduce the impact on the power system.

Although some electric vehicles have been introduced in Sri Lanka, e.g. under initiatives led by the Lanka Electric Vehicle Association,⁵ their effect of electric vehicles on the Sri Lankan electrical power system has not been investigated. This effect should also be considered in any future grid integration study.

Suggested action: The CEB should include a high-demand scenario that includes distributed storage (representing electrical vehicles) in future LTGEPs.

6.2.3 Revisit an interconnection with India

An interconnection with India would allow Sri Lanka to use the Indian electrical system for balancing.

The LTGEP acknowledges that the engineering challenges of building an interconnection to India are not insurmountable. Such interconnections have been built in many other places before. The costs could be covered through a public-private partnership, through international development financing, or other means. There is also the risk that without appropriate pricing, that the interconnection is

treated as an always-on generator rather than an aide to balancing. The interconnection will have to be sized and operated so as to minimize costs and maximize the overall benefits to Sri Lanka. Such a design study should be carried out as part of a wider grid integration study.

Suggested action: The CEB and the private sector in Sri Lanka and abroad should revisit an interconnection with India with a view to maximizing the positive impact under different scenarios.

6.3 Economic viability and financing

Renewable energy facilities appear to be economically viable within the framework provided by the Government of Sri Lanka and the CEB, and can be financed through local and international institutions.

However, there appears to be a significant bureaucratic load in developing new energy facilities in Sri Lanka, as well as foreign-exchange risk. These barriers serve to slow the deployment of renewable energy in Sri Lanka.

Suggested action: The CEB, Sri Lankan Government, and the private sector in Sri Lanka and abroad should seek to streamline the process of siting, developing, and connecting energy generation, transmission, storage, and distribution facilities of all types. Support may be required from the local and international financial sector to develop methods to offset foreign currency risk.

6.4 Acceptance and awareness

Initial wind and solar energy plants in Sri Lanka have functioned as flagship or demonstration projects that have raised awareness of wind and solar energy amongst politicians, in the energy community, and the general population. There have been attempts to raise acceptance of wind energy projects by building roads and schools as part of wind energy project developments. The Ministry of Power and GIZ are collaborating on a project to improve energy efficiency and awareness through nationwide communications work.⁶

It is highly likely that in Sri Lanka – as elsewhere – public awareness of the importance and viability of renewable energy could be raised, and as a result, public acceptance of renewables. The following are suggested as activities that could support this.

⁵See <https://unfccc.int/>

⁶See <https://www.giz.de>

6.4.1 Train renewable energy workforces

Sri Lanka has respected schools and higher education. However, deployment and integration of wind and solar energy and the use of biomass and bio-fuels requires a workforce with specific skills and so there may be a need to train a cadre of renewable energy experts. This training could be done in conjunction with international suppliers for specific tools or equipment (e.g. for wind turbine maintenance or solar panel installation). Experience in Europe and elsewhere has shown that focused training sessions, for example in resource assessment, energy meteorology, or grid integration, can also help participants identify next steps and have a positive impact on the deployment of renewable energy.

Suggested action: The Sri Lanka private sector, together with international vendors and development agencies, should take steps to train local renewable energy specialists.

6.4.2 Develop opportunities for innovation and entrepreneurialism

It is essential that any solutions to the development and integration of renewable energy in Sri Lanka be closely aligned with local needs and conditions. Outside experts can only help to provide perspective and awareness of new solutions. Experience elsewhere has shown that home-grown solutions tend to be more accepted and successful in the long term than imported solutions.

Developing local stakeholder groups, training a local workforce, and raising awareness of the issues associated with all kinds of energy in Sri Lanka will lead to a desire by some people to “do something”. Not all of these people will have access to the tools – credit, working space, software, or skills – that they need to act on their ideas, which will stifle development.

Suggested action: The Sri Lankan Government and private sector could explore ways to set up small-business incubators focused on renewable energy.

6.4.3 Demonstrate a renewable energy microgrid

Microgrids differ from traditional electrical grids in that they usually connect a few megawatts or less of generating capacity and load. They can have a large number of generators distributed across the geographic footprint of the microgrid, and may also connect many different intermittent loads. Microgrids usually incorporate some form of battery for local balancing. The choice of generator can be customized to take advantage of local condi-

tions, for example good solar or wind resources, or agricultural waste that can be used as fuel directly or as a feedstock. Microgrids can be completely islanded, or connected to a national electrical grid for balancing support.

Research into the design and operation of microgrids that include variable renewable energy sources is ongoing in Germany as part of the C/Sells project.⁷ Results from this and other studies suggest that transitioning to interconnected microgrids would have several benefits compared to traditional electrical grids. They help ensure the reliability of local electrical supplies, and reduce the risk of system-wide failure. They also make it possible for local communities to invest in their own generation capacity as the local economy develops.

A microgrid requires hardware, software, and know-how to safely connect and manage the generators, battery, and load. This is available commercially, e.g. from Pfisterer in Germany.

Suggested action: A commercially-operated microgrid in Sri Lanka, perhaps as part of a megawatt-scale plantation power system, could be set up to demonstrate the advantages and current disadvantages of such a system.

6.4.4 Trial biomass and biofuels for thermal power

One possibility to reduce or avoid the cost of importing fossil fuels and to reduce their carbon emissions is to use locally-grown biomass, biogas, and liquid biofuels in place of fossil fuels. Several existing power plants in Europe have been modified to run on bio fuels (e.g. Drax in the UK), and new plants designed to be run on biofuels have also been built. It is possible that expertise can be transferred directly to Sri Lanka or (more likely) that this experience could be used to help customize solutions to local conditions. The introduction of biofuels may help prompt mechanization of agriculture in Sri Lanka and so the reduction in land available for food would be offset by an increase in productivity. This could mitigate pressure on consumer prices.

Suggested action: A trial of gaseous, liquid, or solid biofuels in a thermal power station could be carried out by an IPP or CEB. This trial could happen together with studies into the feasibility of supplying the necessary amounts of fuel from Sri Lanka. That study should consider aspects such as the amount of land required for such an initiative, and possible impacts on agriculture on Sri Lanka.

⁷see www.csells.net

6.4.5 Demonstrate turbine-integrated storage

Energy can currently be stored in on near wind turbines (i.e. before the point of connection to the electrical grid) using batteries, flywheels, water,⁸ and several other technologies. Such solutions have several benefits, such as the ability to store energy when the grid is curtailed, and the ability to use stored energy to reduce the variability of the energy delivered by a project. Such systems may have a larger effect on balancing in a small islanded grid such as Sri Lanka than in a large, internationally connected grid and as a result should be demonstrated in Sri Lanka.

Suggested action: An IPP could work with CEB and vendors to install turbine-integrated storage and test its use on the electrical grid.

6.4.6 Demonstrate offshore wind turbines

Installing the first offshore wind turbines in a new market can be helpful in identifying barriers to future deployments. The experience can be used to refine the processes used by Governments, developers, and suppliers. Such deployments are typically the smallest possible commercially-viable projects, or may be supported by the Government or vendors to help launch a market.

Suggested action: In collaboration with vendors and developers, the Government of Sri Lanka may wish to identify a site or region for an offshore wind energy demonstration plant.

⁸see www.naturspeicher.de

7 Conclusions

In 2016 Sri Lanka committed to producing 100% of its energy from renewable sources. A recent UNDP / ADB study concluded that this transition is possible without raising the burden on consumers. Despite the Government's commitment, the CEB developed and is implementing a long-term plan that increases the contribution of fossil-fueled power and may make it harder to integrate distributed renewable energy in to the Sri Lanka electrical system.

Fortunately, Sri Lanka is not the first country to embark on a process of energy system development that has also led to tensions between different policy goals or between stakeholder groups. There are many established tools and processes to support such a development and achieve outcomes that satisfy many different goals. Several near- and mid-term actions were suggested in Section 6 of this document and are summarized in Table 2 for reference.

Sri Lanka could therefore leverage international experience, research, and support to make its pledged transition to 100% renewable energy whilst avoiding or mitigating challenges experienced elsewhere.

Table 2. Suggested actions by the public and private sectors in Sri Lanka and internationally to support the deployment and integration of renewable energy in Sri Lanka

Action	Sri Lanka		International	
	Public	Private	Public	Private
Political framework and market regulation				
- Build stakeholder groups	✓	✓	✓	
- Facilitate a "Hard Talk"	✓	✓	✓	
- Provide foundational resource data	✓		✓	✓
- Quantify the potential for offshore wind energy	✓		✓	✓
- Identify renewable energy development zones	✓	✓		
- Explore unbundling the CEB	✓			
Infrastructure capacity and technical feasibility				
- Carry out a renewable energy grid integration study	✓		✓	
- Model impacts of electric vehicles	✓	✓		
- Revisit an interconnection with India	✓	✓	✓	✓
- Streamline processes for development, construction, and interconnection	✓	✓		
- Explore financial needs of suppliers and developers		✓	✓	✓
Acceptance and awareness				
- Train renewable energy workforces	✓	✓	✓	✓
- Develop opportunities for innovation and entrepreneurialism	✓	✓	✓	✓
- Demonstrate a renewable energy microgrid	✓	✓	✓	✓
- Trial biomass and biofuels for thermal power plants	✓	✓	✓	✓
- Demonstrate turbine-integrated storage	✓	✓	✓	✓
- Demonstrate offshore wind turbines	✓	✓	✓	✓

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Organizations Mentioned

The following organizations were mentioned in this document. More details are provided here for reference. The inclusion of an organization here is not meant as an endorsement of that organization. Other public- and private-sector organizations exist that may provide comparable services. The author has no contractual relationship to these organizations at the time of preparing this report. AHK funded the author's travel to Sri Lanka in 2018.

Delegation of German Industry and Commerce in Sri Lanka (AHK Sri Lanka)

From their website: *The Delegation of German Industry and Commerce in Sri Lanka (AHK Sri Lanka) was officially inaugurated on 27th March 2018, with the purpose of enhancing the bilateral economic relationship between Germany and Sri Lanka*

Website: srilanka.ahk.de

Center for Solar Energy and Hydrogen Research (ZSW), Germany

From their website: *Research and development of technologies for the sustainable and climate-friendly generation of electricity, heat, and fuel; transfer of R&D results to market-relevant products; consulting for political decision-makers*

Website: www.zsw-bw.de/en

Fraunhofer Institute for Wind Energy Systems (Fraunhofer IWES), Germany

From their website: *The Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft promotes and engages in internationally networked, application-based research for the direct benefit of the business community and to the advantage of society.*

Website: www.iwes.fraunhofer.de

Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), Germany

Website: www.giz.de/en/worldwide/353.html

National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), USA

From their website: *NREL's scientists and analysts conduct clean energy initiatives around the world to support three key international strategic objectives: economic development, energy security, and environmental protection at home and abroad.*

Website: www.nrel.gov/international

⁹See at [news item at srilanka.ahk.de](http://news.ahk.de)

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